

Relevance of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing Program Vis-À-Vis the Nursing Profession in the 21st Century

Judy N. Vasquez

College of Nursing, University of Cebu-Banilad-Cebu City, Philippines
gar_jud96@yahoo.com

Gavino S. Nuñez II

University of Cebu College of Nursing
gabbynunez2rn@gmail.com

Princess Bañares

College of Nursing, University of Cebu-Banilad-Cebu City, Philippines
cessbanares@gmail.com

Judy Ann O. Ferrater-Gimena

University of Cebu, Cebu City Philippines
jagimena@gmail.com

Marilou T. Milana

College of Nursing, University of Cebu-Banilad, Cebu City, Philippines
mrlmilana@gmail.com

Charielyn Kabahar

College of Nursing, University of Cebu-Banilad, Cebu City, Philippines
kabaharcharielyn@gmail.com

Rithsun J. Mamacos

University of Cebu, Cebu City Philippines
rithsunmamacos123@gmail.com

Publication Date: September 22, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17241770

Abstract

Student outcomes measure the quality of education. Hence, the educational institutions offering the Bachelor of Nursing (BSN) programs are required by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) to conduct a tracer study regularly. This investigation traced the employability of Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school years 2020 to 2023, with

the end view of formulating a proposed program-level intervention plan.

This study utilized the descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted at the various workplaces of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu – Banilad Campus for the school years 2020 to 2023, wherein there were fifty-two (52) graduates. The instrument used in this study is the

modified CHED Graduate Tracer Study [GTS] survey questionnaire. Aside from the face-to-face administration of the survey tool, another means of data collection was Google Forms, wherein the link was sent to each respondent's Facebook Messenger account. Simple percentages and rankings were applied for data analysis. The researchers ensured that the ethical principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, and autonomy were adhered to in this investigation. The result shows that the majority of the respondents were 23 years old, females, passed the licensure examination, underwent the Basic Life Support training, worked locally, worked as professionals, divulged that their college curriculum was related to their job, learned communications skill that is useful in the first job, they considered accepting the job because of career challenge. At the same time, more of them took the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) degree because of the profession's status or prestige, were able to find a job in less than a month as a walk-in applicant, and earned a gross monthly income of Php15,000.00 to below Php 20,000.00. Moreover, all were single during the

survey. Moreover, the respondents divulged that they greatly manifested the College of Nursing's vision as a leading producer of accessible and quality nursing producing globally competent nurses; the College of Nursing's mission to maintain a healthy educational setting which fosters quality performance, satisfaction and life-long learning through research-based instruction and community extension; the College of Nursing's goals in adapting competency standards in instruction learning resources, and educational services, promoting leadership among faculty in the service of the community, and fostering a pool of highly motivated competent and compassionate faculty and students in the pursuit of personal and professional development; the College of Nursing core values (nurturing, unity, respect, service, excellence); the BSN Program Educational Objectives (PEOs), stipulations in the CHED Memorandum Order [CMO] No. 15, Series of 2017 for Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] program and the performance indicators for the BSN program. Moreover, they greatly attained the BSN Program Outcomes (POs).

Keywords: *Nursing education, tracer study, curriculum relevance, Bachelor of Science in Nursing, employability, descriptive, University of Cebu, Cebu City*

INTRODUCTION

Every academic institution aims to produce competent and highly qualified graduates who can eventually compete locally and globally (Cuadra, 2019). Likewise, all Higher Education Institution's (HEIs) objectives are to create proficient and highly trained graduates who can eventually set out in life no matter the situation or the economic stability of the country they are in (Torres & Schugurensky, 2002). Thus, the education and training every graduate can get would ensure better opportunities for all individuals to develop their skills in the lifelong learning perspective, enabling them to adapt to rapidly changing labor market requirements and different conditions (Leberman & McDonald, 2016; Taylor & Hamdy, 2013), which leads to Training and labor market policymakers decide on the configuration of education and training systems, employment policies, and investments (Ehrenberg et al., 2021).

Consequently, the K-12 integration in the ASEAN context helps strengthen universities to compete with the world. This way, the Department of Education (DepEd), Commission on Higher Education (CHED), Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), and the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) must ensure that training, skills, subjects, and courses would fit competition in the world market (Quinto & Posada, 2020).

Moreover, quality nursing education is the utmost concern of the higher education offering nursing programs. This task relies on competent faculty members and deans at the forefront of the nursing academe. Nursing educators are expected to impart quality nursing education in theory and skills to instill the required competencies in the students. In addition, they are also likely to manifest advanced practice roles (Bvumbwe, 2016).

In the 21st century, employability is the most required skill, in addition to technical, practical, and analytical skills, to compete for employment and sustain jobs in the global industrial market (Ismail & Mohammed, 2015). Colleges, schools, and universities must provide education and training to meet the standards of different industry employers set for their specific workforce. Other industries must set different standards, but they would always have characteristics they expect their applicants to possess that would boost institutional objectives (Abbot & Snidal, 2021).

In addition, employability is naturally the main priority of university students upon graduation. The university has increasingly provided a quality education to provide students with the required resources to enhance their employability skills, increase their knowledge, and strengthen their abilities. Those skills, once learned, need to be developed during one's working life, put into practice not only in career hunting and during interviews but also in preparing for personal growth and making the most of opportunities for work experience. With the steady increase in university graduates, student employment opportunities have become incredibly competitive. For a university to remain at the forefront of providing quality education to its students, it must evaluate the results of education and training provided by tracing these graduates (Fernando et al., 2023).

According to the International Labor Organization [ILO] (2022), the total global number of unemployed youths is estimated to reach 73 million in 2022, a slight improvement from 2021 (75 million) but still six million above the pre-pandemic level of 2019. Furthermore, the unemployment rate of young people in Europe and Central Asia (ECA) is projected to be 1.5 percentage points higher than the world average in 2022- 16.4 percent versus 14.9 percent, respectively. There has been substantial progress in reducing youth unemployment for both women and men, but the actual and potential shocks of the war in Ukraine are highly likely to affect the results. Hence, it is crucial for young people's entry into and performance in the labor market that they have vital employability skills (Musa & Idris, 2020). Meanwhile, the unemployment rate of young people in the Asia and Pacific region is projected to reach 14.9 percent in 2022, the same as the global average. However, there are essential divergences between subregions and countries (International Labor Organization [ILO], 2022).

In the Philippines, unemployment decreased from 7.7% in May 2021 to 6.0% in May 2022. Furthermore, it was predicted that 2.93 million people were unemployed, down from 3.74 million during the same last year (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2022). Short-and long-term actions must address young unemployment, including raising the labor market's demand, enhancing adolescents' education and skill levels, and prioritizing projects and programs that increase their employability (Fernandez, 2022).

The global nursing workforce is changing. As experienced nurses age, new graduates enter the profession, and nurses worldwide become increasingly transient, new and expanded roles in nursing are emerging within the dynamic world of healthcare. These transformations bring issues related to loss of knowledge, experience, and leadership, in addition to issues of transition for nurses beginning practice or moving into new roles (Lewis, 2015). Also, the shortage of nurses is causing instability and crisis in health systems and will continue (Teresa-Morales et al., 2023).

There is a larger pool of tertiary graduates; however, many need to gain the relevant skills required for successful integration into the labor market. These students put a strain on publicly funded institutions of higher learning, and many countries with limited resources are struggling to finance the growing needs of a larger student body without compromising the quality of their educational offerings (The World Bank, 2017).

The graduates of higher education institutions must show the world that getting a job in a hospital or any other healthcare facility is a manageable problem. Nowadays, competition among registered nurses is

so stiff because of the overpopulation of professional nurses, given that some hospitals need to hire nurses; instead, they are providing volunteer jobs for nurses to lessen the workload of the employed nurses in the hospital. With this sudden turn of events in nursing, only a few got employed. Hence, hospitals seek qualified individuals competent in knowledge, skills, and attitude (Brosola, n.d.).

The quality of the nursing graduates of an educational institution is the best evaluative tool for the quality of education the school provides (Banua, 2017). Continuous improvement in the quality of nursing education programs is a susceptible issue worldwide, particularly in the Philippines, where many trained registered nurses are exported to developed and developing countries. The assessment of the quality of nursing education programs is usually measured using pass rates in licensure examinations by several government organizations (Appiah, 2020).

Moreover, one trustworthy indication of a school's ability to offer high-quality instruction and services is the feedback graduates provide through tracer studies. Hence, to establish more reliable data that reflects the graduates' employability, tracer studies should be regularly carried out, ideally every other year, and cover a broader scope of graduates from prior years (Deblois, 2021).

The alumni are an excellent source of feedback regarding the program's relevance in the current labor market. Moreover, they are considered the best evidence of a program's effectiveness in employment and positions (Orejana & Resurrection, 2010). The essential aspect of any progressing organization is that it must adhere to a culture of self-evaluation. Through evaluation, it can assess its strengths and weaknesses, particularly the value and quality of the products and services they provide. Every evaluative process aims to optimize the organization's daily functions, policies, and programs by identifying what needs to be changed to be more effective and ideal (Orejana & Resurrection, 2010). One of the strategic actions that every educational institution must take is to conduct a tracer study (Lucitasari & Khannan, 2019). It is a highly effective approach for assessing graduates' locations and performance in the workplace (Cuadra et al., 2019). Furthermore, tracer studies are a way to keep the curriculum current and give graduates specific benefits to increase the marketability of educational programs (Woya, 2019).

A graduate tracer study is a potent tool that can provide valuable information for evaluating the whereabouts and performance of graduates in the workplace (Cuadra, 2019). Therefore, higher education institutions (HEIs) worldwide must conduct a graduate tracer study (GTS) to improve their program offerings in response to the changing needs of the labor market. Commonly, the GTS aims to collect basic information from the graduates, including their educational and employment development (Badiru & Wahome, 2016; Schomburg, 2016; Wahome et al., 2015).

Similarly, in the Philippines, the governing body responsible for all HEIs, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), requires the conduct of GTS to improve the quality of education in the country significantly since most of the results of the board programs are deteriorating. Nursing is one of the board programs that continues to deteriorate, as evidenced by the results of the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination (PNLE), which are primarily associated with the demands of the nursing workforce from other countries. Consequently, HEIs offering nursing programs in the country are mushrooming despite their limited capacity to provide the said program (Sanchez & Diamante, 2017).

There are myriad challenges that educational institutions face in their quest to provide quality education, including the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program. Therefore, I traced the employability of Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school years 2020 to 2023, with the end view of formulating a proposed program-level intervention plan.

Framework

This investigation is enthused on the USEM Model of Knight and Yorke (2004), which identifies four key components comprising understanding (U), skilled practice (S), efficacy beliefs (E), and metacognition (M). A vital feature of the model is that the efficacy beliefs provide a foundation for employability and feed

the U, S, and M components. The E component represents a person's belief that they can impact a situation. It includes a broad range of theoretical contributions. Likewise, The USEM model of Knight and Yorke denotes the set of understanding, skills, and personal attributes – efficacy and metacognition; a gateway for individuals to gain employment and be successful in their chosen occupation, which benefits themselves, the workforce, the community, and the economy (Oliver, 2015; Paadi, 2014).

The USEM model was created for the Skills Plus Project, assessment, learning, and workforce, and it aimed to theorize learning outcomes through employability settings (Soares et al., 2017). This focused on students' understanding and skills based on efficacy and metacognition. Higher education institutions should pay more attention to the personal qualities of the subject (Soares et al., 2016).

The USEM model is widely considered a significant development in employability research since, for the first time, employability was conceptualized concerning other constructs such as skills, subject understanding metacognition, and personal qualities. This model also provides a framework for embedding employability into the curriculum and acknowledges the needs of students, employers, and other stakeholders into considerations (Cole & Tibby, 2012). The work of Knight and Yorke has been vital in developing a definition and model of employability for higher education [HE] (Showcross & Ridgman, 2012).

Self-Determination Theory [SDT] (Deci & Ryan, 1985) distinguishes different types of motivation based on the various reasons or goals that give rise to an action. The most basic distinction is between intrinsic motivation, which refers to doing something because it is inherently interesting or enjoyable, and extrinsic motivation, which refers to doing something because it leads to a separable outcome (Ryan & Stiller, 1991).

Intrinsic motivation has emerged as an essential phenomenon for educators—a natural wellspring of learning and achievement that can be systematically catalyzed or undermined by parent and teacher practices (Ryan & Stiller, 1991). Because intrinsic motivation results in high-quality education and creativity, it is essential to detail the factors and forces that engender versus undermine it (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

To be motivated means to be moved to do something. A person who feels no impetus or inspiration to act is thus unmotivated, whereas energized or activated toward an end is considered motivated. Most everyone who works or plays with others is, accordingly, concerned with motivation, facing the question of how much motivation those others, or oneself, have for a task, and practitioners of all types face the perennial task of fostering more versus less motivation in those around them. Most theories of motivation reflect these concerns by viewing motivation as a unitary phenomenon that varies from very little motivation to act to a great deal of it (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Moreover, extrinsic or controlled motivation embodies those activities that generate specific outcomes in rewards or avoided punishments, whereas perceived autonomy is low. Within extrinsic motivation, a continuum of behavioral regulations reflects how the behavior has been assimilated into the individual's sense of self. The continuum includes external regulation, where behavior is controlled by external incentives such as praise, rewards, and punishment avoidance; introjected regulation when the external contingencies have been internalized and the individual acts to facilitate self-esteem (e.g., exhibit ability) or lessen guilt and avoid demonstration of failure; Identified regulation, where the behavior is explicitly recognized and valued by the individual; and integrated regulation which is then the most autonomous kind of extrinsic motivation and appears when the behavior is fully integrated into personal values and beliefs (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Over three decades of research has shown that the quality of experience and performance can be very different when one behaves for intrinsic versus extrinsic reasons. One purpose of this review is to revisit this classic distinction between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and summarize the functional differences between these two general motivation types. Intrinsic motivation has emerged as an essential phenomenon for educators—a natural wellspring of learning and achievement that can be systematically catalyzed or undermined by parent and teacher practices (Ryan & Stiller, 1991). Because intrinsic motivation results in

high-quality education and creativity, it is essential to detail the factors and forces that engender versus undermine it.

A standard categorization of student motivation is intrinsic and extrinsic (Harter, 1981). Intrinsically motivated students¹ are curious and want to learn, while extrinsically motivated students worry about grades and approval from others (Shawcross & Ridgman, 2012).

Self-efficacy is a person's belief in their ability to complete a task or achieve a goal. It encompasses their confidence in themselves to control their behavior, influence their environment, and stay motivated to pursue their goal. People can have self-efficacy in different situations and domains, such as school, work, relationships, and other vital areas (Cherry, 2024). Albert Bandura (1995) defined self-efficacy as "the belief in one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to manage prospective situations.

According to Bandura (1977, 1986, 1997), self-efficacy beliefs lie at the core of human functioning. It is not enough for individuals to possess the requisite knowledge and skills to perform a task; they must also be convinced that they can successfully perform the required behavior(s) under typical and significantly challenging circumstances. Effective functioning requires skills and efficacy beliefs to execute appropriately—two components that develop jointly as individuals grow and learn. Moreover, these two components of successful human functioning act upon one another in a reciprocal fashion, what Bandura (1997) called 'reciprocal causation,' where the functioning of one component depends, in part, upon the functioning of the other. Self-efficacy is important because it plays a role in how a person feels about himself/herself and whether or not he or she successfully achieves one's goals in life (Cherry, 2024).

The Expectancy-Value Theory postulates that achievement-related choices are motivated by people's expectations for success and subjective task value in particular domains (Leaper, 2011). John William Atkinson developed the expectancy-value theory in the 1950s and 1960s to understand the motivation for achievement of individuals. In the 1980s, Jacquelynne Eccles expanded this research into the field of education (Eccles, 1983).

Expectancies are individuals' beliefs regarding their success on specific tasks they will carry out in the short term or long term (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002). An individual's expectancies are related to their behaviors as well as the choices they make. Expectancies are related to ability beliefs such as self-concept and self-efficacy. Self-concept is a domain-specific concept involving beliefs about one's qualities based on experiences in a specific domain (Bong & Skaalvik, 2003). Self-efficacy is the belief that an individual can successfully engage in a future particular task or series of related tasks (Bandura (1993; 2012).

Expectancy-Value Theory is a theory of motivation that describes the relationship between a student's expectancy for success at a task or achieving a goal and the value of task completion or goal attainment (Wigfield, 1994). Hence, students' achievement and achievement-related choices are most proximally determined by two factors: expectancies for success and subjective task values. Expectancies refer to how confident an individual is in his or her ability to succeed in a task. In contrast, task values refer to how important, valuable, or enjoyable the individual perceives the task (Eccles, 1983).

For example, children are more likely to pursue an activity if they expect to do well and they value the activity. The model further differentiates task value into four components: attainment value (i.e., the importance of doing well), intrinsic value (i.e., personal enjoyment), utility value (i.e., perceived usefulness for future goals), and *cost* (i.e., competition with other goals). According to the expectancy-value model, success and task value expectations are shaped by a combination of factors. These include child characteristics (abilities, previous experiences, goals, self-concepts, beliefs, expectations, interpretations) and environmental influences (cultural milieu, socializers' beliefs and behaviors) (Leaper, 2011)

A number of countries, including China, India, and Brazil, have undertaken a significant restructuring of their tertiary education systems to enhance their reach and effectiveness. Yet, progress has been uneven. Nations across the globe made sure that their national policies prioritized fair access, improved learning, proficient retention, and increased assertion of the success of all qualified students, irrespective of their

circumstances. Both policies and program degrees must be tailored to fit the economy's needs (Marmolejo, 2016).

In the challenges of 21st-century education, higher education stands out as one of the significant keys to coping with reforms through instruction, research, and extension. It has become a big challenge for all Philippine Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to cater these reforms. One way of addressing these concerns is by producing fully-equipped graduates who would use what they have learned in school and apply it in their respective work (Tertiary Education Commission, 2009).

The personal driving force of individuals to do the job they love is their economic development. This also relates to the past learning and skills acquired through education and being taught in school and the addition of experiences through the practice of the profession after graduation (Schleicher, 2012).

The concept of employability has risen to prominence over the past 20 years, gaining remarkable traction in policy-making, organizational life, and society. The term has become popular as an antipode to the policy goal of 'full employment' (Finn, 2000) and the conceptual lynchpin of a new career covenant that claims to supplant long-term organizational career bargains (Kanter, 1989).

The central concept for an employability model is the capability, or the necessary part of specialist expertise is knowing their specialism; they also have the confidence to apply their knowledge and skill within the varied and changing situation to continue developing their knowledge and skills (Sumanasiri, 2011).

In different streams of literature, employability has been defined in various, often related ways. It takes an interdisciplinary approach, combining insights from research on higher education and workplace learning, taking a Western perspective (Romgens et al., 2019).

Graduate employability in context or theory, research, and Debate' highlighted employability's complex, contentious, and multi-faceted nature as a concept and policy (Fakunle & Hingson, 2021). Graduate employability is a set of achievements – skills, understanding, and personal attributes – that makes a graduate more likely to gain employment and be successful in their chosen occupations' (Yorke, 2006).

Focusing on employability is an attempt to influence the supply side of the labor market, i.e., the workplace and the productive capacities and performance. In contrast, the demand side comprises the company's requirements, which depend on the growth dynamic (Weiner et al., 2017). In this capacity, 'employability' gestures to a new arrangement wherein the state and employers are no longer committed to nor deemed responsible for providing those they govern and/or employ with lasting and secure jobs. Instead, individuals' capacity to take the initiative, relentlessly update and improve their knowledge and skills, and be flexible and adaptable, i.e., to work on their employability constantly, has come to be understood as the crux of national, organizational, and individual prosperity (Chertkovskaya et al., 2013).

Moreover, according to Dumlao (2006), employability is the capacity to meet the minimum requirement for a special work or employment position. The occupational opportunities and the nature of the job obtained after graduation speak of the employability of graduates. The effectiveness can be judged according to the graduates' success or failure to use their acquired skills and training in economics. Progress. Likewise, Brown and Hesketh (2004) defined employability as the relative chances of getting and maintaining different kinds of employment.

Employability is primarily conceived as a measurable economic outcome for graduates and institutions. This points out both the importance of graduates as critical contributors to economic development and the role of higher education in facilitating the development of graduates for the labor market. At the same time, the seeming consensus regarding employability as an outcome concerning employment or employment rates belies the complexity surrounding the concept in the broader literature. Early on, we want to point out that, related to this complexity, we acknowledge that higher education institutions' educational, research, and service aims are not limited to developing graduate employability (Agasisti et al., 2011; McCowan, 2015).

Williams et al. (2016) suggested that the literature emphasizes three dimensions of employability: capital components, career management, and contextual components. The capital components include

human capital (skills the individual possesses that enhance economic productivity), social and cultural capital, and psychological capital. Psychological capital is related to how employability can be improved by individual characteristics, such as 'confidence, hope resilience, positive self-evaluation and personality traits such as conscientiousness' Career management has two parts: signal management and self-management. Both aspects reiterate the importance of the individual's ability to navigate the world of employment concerning job acquisition and relevant training (Luthans, 2002).

Employability is practiced in different circumstances; the first is through learning agility. Learning agility reflects the wholesomeness of an individual to impose the skills on the current job one is facing. This is the fundamental ability to learn, adapt, unlearn, and relearn in varied life conditions and scenarios (Mitchinson & Morris, 2014).

Knibbs et al. (2015) opined that employability challenges whether academic and support staff involved in employability and enterprise-related learning, teaching, and support services (e.g., careers and placement offices; incubator, accelerator, and start-up hubs) are fulfilling the needs of all higher education stakeholders.

In this manner, employability appears as an agenda for activating employment expenditures by promoting training programs, services, more or less targeted subsidies that favor hiring or maintenance in the job, and through a varied gamut of incentive or authoritarian measures to put the unemployed back to work. The process is meant to be individualized and preventive, mirrored in the slogan about shifting from job protection to security through employability (Weiner et al., 2017).

The ability of higher education to contribute to employability is, however, an old debate outside the scope of this particular issue. Despite this, the tendency to regard the purpose of education as more than for its own sake puts employability at the center of debates on the social and economic responsibility of higher education (Fakunle & Hingson, 2021). Likewise, Fletcher-Brown et al. (2015) disclosed that students identified involvement in real live-client projects, applying knowledge learned in the classroom to solve a business problem, enabled them to develop skills demanded by employers. Clients noted how student work exceeded expectations, providing tangible outputs and innovative ideas for their business, even though there were limited periods of interaction. The employability construct represents a scientific challenge to understand better the relationship between job seekers' issues and expectations of the world of work (Guilbert, 2015).

Nursing has always been considered to be one of the noblest professions. It has always been regarded as pro-human, and nurses have been known for their selfless caring and tireless service regardless of someone's economic status (Guinid et al., 2019). The Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) is a four-year program with general education and professional courses. Professional courses are threaded through the first and fourth years, emphasizing the nursing concepts with corresponding Related Learning Experience (RLE). The BSN program provides an intensive nursing practice that will refine further the nursing competencies to ensure the achievement of the BSN program outcomes required of an entry-level nurse (Commission on Higher Education [CHED], 2017).

Further, The Commission on Higher Education [CHED] Memorandum Order No. 15, series of 2017, stipulates that the BSN program aims to develop a professional nurse who can assume entry-level positions in health facilities or community settings. The professional nurse is capable of providing safe, human, quality, and holistic care to individuals of varying ages, genders, and health-illness statuses, as well as the health of at-risk families, population groups, and communities, singly or in collaboration with other health care providers to promote health, prevent illness, restore health, alleviate suffering and provide end of life care.

Filipino nurses are in high demand globally because of the standardized and unified nursing curriculum for a Bachelor of Science. This globalized demand leads to the mushrooming of nursing schools, threatening Filipino nurses' image abroad. Furthermore, this also worsens the country's health services and nursing education (Crisostomo, 2013).

After graduation, graduates are often tasked with a greater responsibility in looking for a job. Crucially, the ability of a graduate to realize or actualize things that he learned from school depends on the individual's personal and external circumstances and the inter-relationship between the two (Tabbuac, 2010). However, students with a low employability level tend to blame the universities' poor and outdated curriculum and the lack of market-driven focus (Tran, 2015).

In previous years, nurses were in demand overseas, driving Filipinos away from the country (Tabbuac, 2010). This global demand for nurses has led to a sudden surge in nursing schools in the Philippines (Bengan, 2011). This has led to the mass migration of nurses, even prompting doctors to take up nursing. However, there currently needs to be more nurses to be employed here and abroad. Health institutions in the country do not offer new items for hiring nurses. On the other hand, getting their work abroad is complicated and requires many expenses from the nurse who wants to apply (Tabbuac, 2010).

The impression of HEIs in the Philippines is likely tangled with its reputation of generating graduates who would undoubtedly acquire a good and stable job after graduation (Cuadra et al., 2019). However, institutions mostly need to measure the quality of education they provide. According to a study by Zimmerman (2012), the first two years of college give almost half of the students with minor learning. Forty-five percent of the students had no gains in learning. Students were more focused on their social lives, while their mentors focused more on doing their research than teaching. The study also revealed that among the 3,000 respondents, socializing and sleeping comprise seventy-five percent of their time, while sixteen percent was spent studying.

Pool and Sewel (2007) posit that career development learning has yet to be strongly represented in Higher Education Institutions [HEI's] employability strategies (Johnes, 2006). Training and labor market policymakers decide on the configuration of education and training systems, employment policies, and investments (Ehrenberg et al., 2021). The deans of nursing schools should provide recognition for all the hardships and hard work of the faculty members for sharing their expertise and motivation inside the classroom (Bvumbwe, 2016). Apart from the qualified faculty, curriculum enhancement is essential to the nursing academe as it guides all educators to elevate the standards of nursing education. Fawaz et al. (2018) elaborated that nursing education aims to develop nurses capable of providing safe, quality nursing care that adapts to evolving conditions. Moreover, a nurse educator must consider that the students must receive all learning experiences, including theories and skills, through multiple channels, and students must have access to them at the best possible times.

There is a need to understand and appreciate discipline and how organizations work as skillful practices in academics, employment, and life (Jackson, 2015). Skills reflect professional practices with the implication that this hinges on awareness of and responsiveness to the context in contrast to the narrowly-conceived notions of skills such as appearing at the lower end of the 'essential skills. There is a need to understand the knowledge and skills needed for young professionals to be a more effective and efficient part of the industry (Gerwe, 2021).

Brown and Hesketh (2004) developed and introduced employability in the marketing program in higher education. It employed students to have live-client learning activities in a small to medium enterprise, which enhanced students' economic and local community awareness apart from being used or having a business. Also, the students should learn to be self-aware in researching the job markets to see what opportunities are available to help them prepare themselves to be more marketable to possible employers (Johnes, 2006).

It is, therefore, important that schools keep track of their graduates to determine the extent of progress they made in their adjustments to the world of work. Further, through follow-up of graduates, some information that suggests the need for improvement of the school program, data essential to continuous appraisal and modification of curriculum, and other services will be gathered (Tabbuac, 2010). The teaching content must be updated, and assessment processes must be streamlined to bring more practical professional knowledge to reduce students' struggles to move from higher education to employment (Mason & Watts, 2009).

Hafiz (2020) mentioned that a tracer study is a graduate or alumni survey that attempts to track the activities of former students of an academic institution. Universities can utilize tracer study results to determine the success of the educational process for their students.

According to Dotong et al. (2016), the employability of graduates is one of the measures of Higher Education Institutions to ensure that the quality of education they provide is suitable to the needs of the industry.

It is essential for program improvement to emphasize graduate tracer study (GTS) (Quinto & Posada, 2020). Mwakigonja (2016) in Tanzania allowed subsequent curriculum review and the introduction of complete modularization and competency-based learning. It is envisioned that the tracer study findings will improve teaching learning and inform the following curriculum review, leading to increased output of appropriately trained health professionals to fill the big gap in human resources.

Graduate tracer studies are essential for understanding the relevance and quality of programs offered by universities and the labor market (Quinto & Posada, 2020). Cuadra et al. (2019) stated that a graduate tracer study is a powerful tool that can provide valuable information for evaluating the whereabouts and performance of graduates in the workplace. Moreover, graduate tracer studies (GTS) are essential tools to monitor education output.

Tracing graduates will provide rich knowledge about the situation, which will help broaden viewpoints among administrators, faculty, and students. Such knowledge as the economic sector, current job title, duration of search for the first job, methods of job search, values developed and practiced in work, and skills acquired are relevant for higher education institutions to note. The university graduate tracer study provides the desirable information as to what happens to graduates when they join the world of work. It is equally important to find out how adequately the institution offers training in the overall performance of their career life and the extent to which the knowledge, communication, and other skills have been developed (Fernando et al., 2023).

According to Schomburg (2003), tracer studies, also known as graduate studies, alumni research, or follow-up studies, target higher education graduates to get information indicating possible deficits in a given educational program and serve as a basis for future planning activities. Typically, tracer studies must be conducted between 6 months and three years because surveys are one type of empirical research that can give helpful information for analyzing the outcomes of a given institution of higher education's education and training. It may gather vital information on graduates' career profiles, undergraduate experience, first and current jobs, and the significance of their educational background and job-specific abilities. Graduate tracer studies can also collect information on the relevance of the curriculum and the satisfaction of graduates with their academic preparation.

A tracer study, according to the European Training Foundation (ETF), is a "retrospective analysis of graduates by a structured survey, which takes place sometime after graduation" (generally between 6 months and three years). The graduate survey, alumni survey, or graduate track are all terms for the same thing. The target population is usually a homogeneous group of students/trainees who graduated simultaneously (generation or graduation cohort) (Fernando et al., 2023).

Egesah and Wahome (2017) explained that the Graduate Tracer Study (GTS) is important in the utilization of feedback from graduates for the improvement of teaching and learning spaces, conditions, provisions, and programs. One recent and innovative way of ensuring quality learning at universities worldwide is using feedback from graduates to improve teaching and learning spaces, conditions, provisions, and programs. This way, feedback can be obtained and used from graduate tracer studies (GTS).

The graduate tracer study (GTS) of Austria (2023) aimed to improve the program offerings of the state college, especially its Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN). A descriptive survey was employed to collect the nursing graduates' demographic, educational, and employment profiles, as well as feedback for the improvement of the program. There were 247 nursing graduates from 2006-2007 to 2014-2015. The study employed 60% representative stratified and snowball samplings in tracing the graduates. Findings were tabulated using frequency distribution tables. Feedbacks were grouped into themes. The demographic

profile showed varied ages of the graduates, from 20 to 40, who were predominantly female. The educational profile showed fluctuating nurse licensure examination (NLE) percentage performance of the graduates and many who were not actively involved in nursing-related continuing professional development (CPD). The employment profile showed many graduates who were not employed in nursing-related jobs and were not permanently employed. Overall, these findings corroborated the graduates' feedback that to produce quality graduates in response to the needs of the labor market, program offerings-improvement of HEIs in terms of faculty, curriculum and instruction, library, and physical facilities are needed. Keywords: Graduate Tracer Study, Nurse Licensure Examination, Continuing Professional Development, Employment.

Alao, thw tracer study by Brosola (n. d.) evaluated the employability of Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates at the National University. This descriptive design study involved the graduates from the academic year (AY) 2007 to 2018. The total population sampling was utilized. The total number of graduates from AY 2007 to 2018 is 349. However, only 85 graduates participated. The tool was administered to the graduates through their email and Facebook Messenger. The results showed that few graduates completed higher academic degrees: one point two percent currently taking Doctor of Medicine; one point two percent completed the Master of Arts in Nursing and Master of Science in Nursing degrees.

Meanwhile, one point two percent obtained a Master of Business Administration degree; one point two percent had taken foreign licensure examinations for nurses. Meanwhile, thirty-two point nine percent were employed as hospital staff nurses; twenty-seven percent took almost a year to get a job after graduation; forty-seven percent accepted their current job because of its relatedness to the nursing profession. It is concluded that there may be many challenges in finding nurses' jobs, but the graduates managed to land a job related to nursing. It is recommended that other methods and strategies should be employed to increase the response rate in the survey. The continuity of a graduate tracer study would be implemented.

In addition, the study of Hipona et al. (021) aimed to keep track of the graduates in the La Consolacion University Philippines under the Bachelor of Science in Nursing from 2016-2020. The descriptive type of research was utilized via online survey questionnaires in Google Forms as the primary tool to gather the information needed from the respondents. The primary data sources are the 10 nursing graduates of La Consolacion University Philippines, College of Allied Medical Professions from batch 2016-2020. According to the findings, most graduates work in nursing-related occupations, mainly private institutions. Furthermore, the graduates believe that the BS Nursing program at LCUP has helped them grow emotionally and professionally.

Objectives of the Study

This study traced the employability of Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school years 2020 to 2023, with the end view of formulating a proposed program-level intervention plan. Specifically, this study aims to present the following: 1) profile of the respondents in terms of their gender, and civil status; 2) reasons in taking the Bachelor Science in Nursing (BSN) course and professional examination results; 3) trainings and advanced studies attended and reasons for pursuing advanced studies; 4) employment data such as their employment status, the reason for unemployment, place of work, and present occupation; 5) length of time in finding the first job, strategies used to find the first job; 6) gross monthly income; 7) relevance of the curriculum to the first job, competencies learned in college that are useful in the first job, relatedness of the job to college course, and reasons for accepting the job; manifestation/attainment of the attributes stipulated in the college vision, mission, goals, and core values, Program Educational Objective (PEO), Program Outcomes (PO), competencies stipulated CMO No. 15 that is specific to Bachelor of Science in Nursing and the performance indicators.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the discussions on the research design, research environment, research respondents, data gathering procedure, treatment of data and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive survey research design to determine the employability of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school years 2020-2023.

A descriptive study is designed to describe the distribution of one or more variables without regard to any causal or other hypothesis (Aggarwal & Ranganathan, 2019).

Descriptive survey research is a time-efficient research method, descriptive survey design engages the people at the center of the research objective. The survey design method enables vast amounts of data to be gathered from a heterogeneous audience. The survey design helps to analyze the frequencies and identify patterns in the survey responses. Descriptive survey designs are used for the following purpose in market research: understanding the demographic of a market or population (country-wise or region-wise), examining audiences' opinion on the company's offering and gauging customer satisfaction with the company offering and customer support (Voxco, 2021).

Research Environment

The study was conducted at the various workplaces of the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) of the University of Cebu – Banilad Campus for the school years 2020 to 2023.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were the fifty-two (52) graduates of Bachelor of Science in Nursing [BSN] of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school years 2020-2023. Convenience sampling technique was used to identify research respondents respondents.

Table 1. Year Graduated of the Respondents (n= 52)

School Year	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
2022-2023	27	51.92
2021-2022	10	19.23
2020-2021	15	28.85

Twenty-seven (27) or 51.92 % of the respondents were graduates for the school year in 2022-2023, ten (10) consisting of 19.23% were graduates for S.Y. 2021-2022, and fifteen (15, 28.85%) were graduates for the S.Y. 2022-2023.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in this study is the modified CHED Graduate Tracer Study [GTS] survey questionnaire. This contains questions about the 1) profile of the respondents in terms of their gender, and civil status; 2) reasons in taking the Bachelor Science in Nursing (BSN) course and professional examination results; 3) trainings and advanced studies attended and reasons for pursuing advanced studies; 4) employment data such as their employment status, the reason for unemployment, place of work, and present occupation; 5) length of time in finding the first job, strategies used to find the first job; 6) gross monthly income; 7) relevance of the curriculum to the first job, competencies learned in college that are useful in the first job, relatedness of the job to college course, and reasons for accepting the job;

manifestation/attainment of the attributes stipulated in the college vision, mission, goals, and core values, Program Educational Objective (PEO), Program Outcomes (PO), attributes stipulated in CMO No. 15, series of 2017 that is specific to Bachelor of Science in Nursing and the performance of indicators.

Research Procedures

The researchers sent a letter to the campus director and the dean of the College of Nursing for approval to conduct the study. Another letter was given to the Registrar's Office requesting the overall population of the graduates for the school years 2020-2023 and asking for a permit to gain access to the latter's contact information, including the home address of the graduates and their landline/cell phone numbers and email address.

After all the requests were approved, the researchers gave the target respondents the tool when they visited the school. To guarantee the maximum involvement of the participants and retrieval of the data, the researchers contacted and informed the research respondents about the survey. They also made follow-ups through their contact information. Another means of administering the survey questionnaire was that the contents were transferred to Google Forms, and the link was sent to each of their Facebook Messenger accounts.

Treatment of Data

Simple percentage was used to determine the profile of the respondents, while ranking was applied to determine the trainings or advanced studies attended after college, reason for unemployment, utilized academic and nursing competencies learned in college.

Research Ethics Protocol

The researchers ensured that the ethical principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, justice, and autonomy were adhered to in the conduct of this investigation. The results of this study will be helpful in the formulation of the program-level intervention plan to address the shortcomings and weaknesses of the existing BSN programs. The plan also aims to ensure that the University of Cebu-Baniald's BSN program will be enhanced. Before the data collection, orientation about the purpose of the study was done so that each respondent understood their rights and the nature of the survey before being asked to sign the Informed Consent Form (ICF). This protocol was reviewed by the University of Cebu Academic Research Ethics Committee (UCAREC) to obtain approval for the Certificate of Protocol. All the data were handled with utmost confidentiality, and de-identification was observed to protect the identity of the research respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their gender, and civil status; 2) reasons in taking the Bachelor Science in Nursing (BSN) course and professional examination results; 3) trainings and advanced studies attended and reasons for pursuing advanced studies; 4) employment data such as their employment status, the reason for unemployment, place of work, and present occupation; 5) length of time in finding the first job, strategies used to find the first job; 6) gross monthly income; 7) relevance of the curriculum to the first job, competencies learned in college that are useful in the first job, relatedness of the job to college course, and reasons for accepting the job; manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the college vision, mission, goals, and core values, Program Educational Objective (PEO), Program Outcomes (PO), and competencies stipulated CMO No. 15 that is specific to Bachelor of Science in Nursing, and the performance indicators.

This part presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, civil status, year graduated and professional examination taken. Table 2 and Figure 1 presents the frequency and percentage of each age group.

Table 2. Age of the Respondents (n=52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
25 years old	4	7.69
24 years old	13	25.00
23 years old	29	55.77
22 years old	6	11.54
21 years old	0	0

Figure 1. Age of the Respondents

Out of the fifty-five (55) total respondents, twenty-nine (29), or 55.77%, were 23 years old, while the four (4), or 7.69% of the respondents were 25 years old. These figures denote that predominantly, more of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates for the school years 2020 to 2023 belonged to the young adult age group and that they were new in their job or at the entry level to the labor force in the healthcare industry since they graduated a few years ago.

Figure 2 presents the gender of the respondents.

Table 3. Gender of the Respondents (n=52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Female	30	57.69
Male	22	42.31

Figure 2. Gender of the Respondents

Of the fifty-two respondents, thirty, or 57.69 %, were females, while the twenty-two (22, 42.31%) were males. This data indicates that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu were dominated by ladies since they have the inherent passion and abilities to provide care to people.

According to Teresa-Morales et al. (2023), the main reasons for choosing a nursing degree were associated with fulfillment and a desire to help others and interact with them. The reasons for completing their studies were primarily related to an interest in providing professional care, showing a more profound and concrete knowledge of nursing care work.

Figure 4 presents the civil status of the respondents.

Table 4. Civil Status of the Respondents (n= 52)

Indicator	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Single	52	100

Fifty-two (52) or 100% of the respondents were single during the study. This information indicates that new Bachelor of Science in Nursing Graduates prioritize their career or professional nursing practice over starting a family. This situation relates to the fact that employees at the entry-level usually receive low salaries, which means they need to be more able to support their families. Also, most of the Bsngraduates in the country focused on gaining hospital experience. Then, they will seek employment abroad or migrate to developed countries for better nursing careers with higher pay.

Table 5 shows the data about the reasons for taking the Bachelor of Science in Nursing course at the University of Cebu-Banilad.

Table 5. Reasons for Taking the Course for Undergraduate Degrees (n=52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
High grades in the course or subject related to the course	3	5.77
Good grades in high school	4	7.69
Influence of parents and relatives	3	5.77
Peer influence	5	9.62
Inspired by a role model	1	1.92
Strong passion for the profession	8	15.38
Prospect for immediate employment	4	7.69
Status or prestige of the profession	10	19.23
Availability of course offering in chosen institution	5	9.62
Prospect of career advancement	2	3.85
Affordable for the family	2	3.85
Prospect of attractive compensation	1	1.92
Opportunity for employment abroad	4	7.69

Ten (10) or 19.23 % of the respondents chose the Bachelor of Science in Nursing course because of the profession's prestige, while one (1, 1.92%) was because of a role model that he or she followed. These pieces of information show that more of the graduates of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) for the school years 2020 to 2023 were enticed to study the BSN course because they had observed that when they become registered nurses, the people in society will have high respect to them and that they have a great opportunity to migrate and work to developed countries and be able to earn huge income, which uplifts their life standing.

Table 6 shows the data about the professional examination results of the respondents.

Table 6. Professional Examination Result (n= 52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Passed	45	86.54
Failed	7	13.46

Forty-five (52) respondents, comprising 86.54%, passed the professional licensure examination, while seven (7) or equivalent to 13.46% failed. This information implies that predominantly the the Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school years 2020-2022 pass the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination (PNLE). Thereby, it can be deduced that the BSN curriculum and delivery of instruction enabled the students to grasp the nursing theories and principles, which prepared them to become successful in the licensure examination and future examinations that they may take when they seek employment abroad like NCLEX, TOEFL, and others.

Table 7 shows the information about the trainings or advanced studies attended after college as well as the reason for pursuing advanced studies.

Table 7. Trainings/Advanced Studies Attended after College (n=52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Rank
1. Basic Life Support	13	1
2. Infectious and communicable diseases Training Seminar	7	4
3. Intravenous Training and Blood Transfusion	9	3
4. New Zealand Diploma Level 7	3	6.5
5. Private Nurse Training	10	2
6. Sacred Heart Hospital Staff Nurse Training	2	8
7. Neonatal Resuscitation Program	1	9
8. Lactation Management Program	5	5
9. National Competency II Training - EMS	3	6.5
Reason for Pursuing Advance Studies:		
1. Promotion	12	23.08
2. Professional Development	40	76.92

The top three (3) pieces of training which the research respondents attended after they graduated from the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) course at the University of Cebu-Banilad in the years 2020 to 2022 are Basic Life Support (ranked first), New Private Nurse Training (ranked second), and Infectious and Communicable Diseases Training Seminar (ranked third). The graduates took these different pieces of training to enhance their skills in providing nursing services, mainly when they work in the hospital or when they provide specialized nursing care outside the hospital premises, like as a home health care nurse, which entails providing one-on-one care for patients in their homes. These patients can be elderly, critically ill, or disabled, or they may be recovering from surgery, injury, or accident. In-home nurses can assist pregnant women and new mothers with ongoing care, support, and education.

Table 8 shows the present employment status of the respondents who are graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) of the University of Cebu-Banilad.

Table 8. Present Employment Status of the Graduates (n = 52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Regular or Permanent	24	46.15
Temporary	10	19.23
Casual	3	5.77
Contractual	5	9.62
Self-employed	10	19.23

Sixteen (24), or 46.15% of the graduate respondents, had a regular employment status, while three (3), or equivalent to 5.77%, had a casual job status. It can be noted in the data that ten (10, 19.23%) respondents were self-employed and had five (5, 9.62%) contractual employment status. This information implies that more Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad were employed at various healthcare facilities in the country and abroad. The demand for professional nurses is high, not only in the Philippines but also abroad, like the Middle Eastern nations, the United Kingdom, Singapore, New Zealand, Australia, and even Japan. Hence, it is easy for nursing graduates to be employed after graduation and even after passing the licensure examinations.

It can be noted that there were another ten (10 or 19.23%) self-employed respondents. These registered nurses ventured into business endeavors while applying what they had learned in nursing entrepreneurship.

Nurse entrepreneurs leverage their healthcare background, creativity, business systems knowledge, and successful investment strategies to develop their own businesses in the healthcare industry. Nurse entrepreneurs as a nurse who leverage their healthcare background along with creativity, business systems knowledge, and successful investment strategies to develop their businesses in the healthcare industry (Maryville University, 2023).

Table 9 shows the information for the respondents' reasons for unemployment.

Table 9. Reasons for Unemployment of the Graduates (n =30)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Rank
Advance or further studies	20	1
No job opportunity	7	2
Did not look for job	3	3

* *Multiple Responses*

Of the fifty-five (55) respondents, thirty (230) were not working or unemployed at the time of the survey. Their foremost reason for their unemployment was that they were still taking advanced or further studies (ranked first), had no job opportunities (ranked second), and did not look for a job (ranked third). This implies that there were Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad who chose to enhance their capabilities through training and forego any employment opportunities first with the hope that once they can work abroad, they can gain a high income.

Table 10 presents the data about the place of work of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates for school years 2020 to 2023.

Table 10. Place of Work of the Respondents (n = 52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Local	29	55.77
Abroad	23	44.23

Of fifty-two (52) Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad, twenty-nine (29), or 55.77 %, worked here in the Philippines, while twenty-three (23), or 44.23%, worked abroad during the time of the survey. This information implies that most graduates were still working in the country. Still, many already had work outside the Philippines, like in Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), the United Kingdom (UK), Singapore, New Zealand, Australia, Canada, and many more.

Table 11 presents the line of business of the company where the graduate works for their first job.

Table 11. Present Occupation of the BS Nursing Graduates (n=52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Officials of Government and Special-interest Organizations, Corporate Executives, Managers, Managing Proprietors and Supervisors	10	19.23
Professionals	24	46.15
Clerks	8	15.38
Service workers and Shop/Market Sales workers	5	9.61
Special Occupation	5	9.61

Of the fifty-two (52) respondents, twenty-four (24 or 46.15%) were employed as professionals, ten (10, 19.23)% worked as officials of government and special-interest organizations, corporate executives, managers, managing proprietors and supervisors, eight (8, 15.38%) worked as a clerk, five (5, 9.61%) were service workers and another five (5, 9.61%) were into a particular occupation. This data shows that most Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu- Banilad for the school years 2020 to 2023 exercise their nursing profession in various healthcare facilities like hospitals and other health-related establishments.

Table 12 shows the data about the length of time the Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad (batches 2020 to 2023) were able to find a job.

Twenty-two (22) or 42.31% of the graduates were able to find a job in less than a month, while twelve (12, 23.08%) graduates were able to find a job in 1 to 6 months, eight (8, 15.38%) were able to find work in 7 to 11 months, five (5, 9.61%) were able to find work in 1 year to less than two years, two (2, 3.45%) were able to find a job in 1 year to less than three years, and one (1, 1.92%) were able to find a job in 3 years to less than four years.

Table 12. Length of Time in Finding the First Job (n=52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Less than a month	22	42.31
1 to 6 months	12	23.08
7 to 11 months	8	15.38
1 year to less than 2 years	5	9.61
1 year to less than 2 years	2	3.84
2 years to less than 3 years	2	3.84
3 years to less than 4 years	1	1.92

This means that the Bachelor of Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad were highly employable in the healthcare industry and related medical fields. Currently, the demand for professional nurses is high in hospitals in the Philippines and many countries in Asia, Europe, Oceania, and the United States of America, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 13 presents the frequency distribution of Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu- Banilad regarding how they find their first job.

Table 13. Strategies Used to Find the First Job (n = 52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Response to an advertisement	11	21.15
As walk-in applicant	14	26.92
Recommended by someone	5	9.92
Information from friends	7	13.46
Arranged by school's job placement officer	10	19.23
Job Fair	5	9.92

Fourteen (14), or 26.92%, of the respondents, found their first job through the walk-in application, while only five (5, 9.92%) applied at the job fair and were recommended by someone. These survey results mean that Bachelor of Science Nursing graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad were able to find a job on their efforts since there are lots of hospitals, healthcare facilities, and even business process outsourcing (BPOs) in which the nature of services relates to healthcare were hiring nurses. This means that finding a job for nurses in Cebu City is easy and that applicants can find a job or work independently. The walk-in application also means that the BSN graduates referred to newspaper and/ or online advertisements to look for job vacancies. Also, friends' referrals and ideas for job opportunities were very helpful for them in getting employment.

Table 14 presents the data about the gross monthly income of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school years 2020-2023.

Twenty-three or 44.23% of the respondent graduates earned a gross monthly income of Php15,000.00 to below Php 20,000.00. At the same time, only one (1) or 1.92% earned below Php5,000.00. These results imply that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad earned a salary above the minimum wage for Region 7 (Central Visayas).

Table 14. Gross Monthly Income of the Graduates (n= 52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Php 25,000.00 and above	3	5.77
Php 20,000.00 - below Php 25,000.00	2	3.85
Php 15,000.00 - below Php 20,000.00	23	44.23
Php 10,000.00 - below Php 15,000.00	18	34.62
Php 5,000.00 - below Php 10,000.00	5	9.62
Below Php 5,000.00	1	1.92

However, this salary level is for entry-level nurses since it is low if they work in government hospitals or health units. Moreover, these nurses tend to gain hospital experience as an entry career. They will seek employment abroad wherein their salary is twice, thrice, or ten times higher than the amount they received at the study's time.

Table 15 presents the respondents' assessment of the relevance of the curriculum to the first job.

Table 15. Relevance of the Curriculum to the First Job (n = 52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Yes	36	69.23
No	16	30.77

Thirty-six (36), or 69.23% of the respondents divulged that their college curriculum was related to their job. This data indicates that the majority of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates were able to land a job wherein they could exercise their profession. They worked in hospitals, healthcare service providers, and other entities in which the nature of operation relates to nursing.

On the other hand, only sixteen (16), or 30.77%, disclosed that their current work (at the time of the survey) is irrelevant to the curriculum. Understandably, these respondents had jobs unrelated to the nursing profession. Hence, they cannot say that the knowledge they learned from the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) is connected to their first job. This group of graduates just took unrelated jobs as an entry-level career.

Table 16 shows the competencies learned that are useful in the first job of the graduate respondents.

Table 16. Competencies Learned in that are Useful in the First Job

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Rank
Communication Skills	36	1st
Human Relations Skills	30	3rd
Entrepreneurial Skills	32	2 nd
Information Technology Skills	24	5 th
Problem Solving Skills	28	4 th

Forty-eight (42), or equivalent to 80.77% of the respondents, disclosed that their undergraduate degree was relevant to their first job, while only ten (10) respondents, or 19.23%, said that their course was unrelated to their first job. These results mean that the majority of the BSN graduates for the school years 2020 to 2023 viewed that the knowledge they learned in the different subjects they took while they were studying at the University of Cebu-Banilad was applicable in the course of their performance in their job as nurses. However, there were instances in which some graduates could land jobs unrelated to the nursing course they took, especially if they were still at the entry level of their careers. Also, some graduates could find jobs for which the salary level is higher if they work in hospitals in the Philippines. Hence, they grab the opportunity to earn a high income, especially if they already have a family to support.

Table 17 shows the respondents' reasons for accepting the job.

Table 17. Relatedness of the Job to the College Course (n= 52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Yes	42	80.77
No	10	19.23

Forty-eight (42), or equivalent to 80.77% of the respondents, disclosed that their undergraduate degree was relevant to their first job, while only ten (10) respondents, or 19.23%, said that their course was

unrelated to their first job. These results mean that the majority of the BSN graduates for the school years 2020 to 2023 viewed that the knowledge they learned in the different subjects they took while they were studying at the University of Cebu-Banilad was applicable in the course of their performance in their job as nurses. However, there were instances in which some graduates could land jobs unrelated to the nursing course they took, especially if they were still at the entry level of their careers. Also, some graduates could find jobs for which the salary level is higher if they work in hospitals in the Philippines. Hence, they grab the opportunity to earn a high income, especially if they already have a family to support.

Table 18 shows the respondents' reasons for accepting the job.

Table 18. Reasons for Accepting the Job (n = 52)

Indicators	Frequency (f)	Rank
Salaries & benefits	10	3rd
Career Challenge	22	1st
Related to special skills	5	4th
Proximity to residence	15	2nd

**Multiple Responses*

Twenty-two (22) respondents answered that they considered accepting the job because of career challenge (ranked first), then proximity to residence (ranked second), salaries and benefits (ranked third), and lastly, related to special skills. The primary consideration of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates in looking for a job is its relatedness to their bachelor's degree since they can efficiently perform the job since they have specialized knowledge that they learned from the training from the school. The quality of educational services provided to the students at the College of Nursing of the University of Cebu is comprehensive and extensive, combined with skilled-based training. Hence, the graduates would be looking for challenges in the career they will embark upon after passing the licensure examinations.

This section presents the data concerning the manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the college vision, mission, and goals, Program Educational Objectives (PEO), and attainment of the Program Outcomes (PO) for the Bachelor of Science Nursing (BSN) of the University of Cebu-Banilad.

Table 19 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the College of Nursing vision.

Table 19. Respondents' Manifestation of the College of Nursing Vision (n= 52)

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
A leading producer of accessible and quality nursing producing globally competent nurses.	3.75	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51 -3.25 -Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

The weighted mean of 3.75 shows that the respondents divulged that they manifested to a great extent the attributes of being graduates of the University of Cebu- Banilad, the leading producer of accessible and quality nursing, producing globally competent nurses. Hence, the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN)

graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school years 2020 to 2023 exhibited the competencies and skills they learned in school in performing their jobs at the healthcare establishments where they were employed during the survey. This information indicates that the quality of educational training at UC molded and prepared its graduates to be competent in providing nursing care even globally.

Table 20 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the College of Hospitality Management mission.

Table 20. Respondents' Manifestation of the Mission of the College of Nursing

(n=52)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Maintain a healthy educational setting which fosters quality performance, satisfaction and life-long learning through research-based instruction and community extension	3.75	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51-3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 -1.75 - Not Manifested

The highest weighted mean of 3.75 shows that the respondents divulged that they manifested to a great extent the attributes of being graduates of the University of Cebu- Banilad, which aims to maintain a healthy educational setting that fosters quality performance, satisfaction, and life-long learning through research-based instruction and community extension. These results indicate that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad for the school years 2020 to 2023 appreciated the quality of educational training they received from the instructors because it molded and prepared them to become globally competent nursing professionals. Also, the training at UC exposed them to class-based instructions, community service, and research-based nursing practice.

Table 21 shows the respondents' assessments on the attainment of the goals of the college of nursing.

Table 21. Respondents' Assessment on the Attainment of the Goals of the College of Nursing (n=52)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Adapt competency standards in instruction learning resources, and educational services	3.77	Highly Attained
2. Promote leadership among faculty in the service of the community.	3.69	Highly Attained
3. Foster a pool of highly motivated competent and compassionate faculty and students in the pursuit of personal and professional development	3.73	Highly Attained
Aggregate Mean	3.73	Highly Attained

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51-3.25- Moderately Manifested; 1.76-2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00-1.75 - Not Manifested

The highest weighted mean of 3.77 shows that the respondents divulged that, to a great extent, the University of Cebu College of Nursing adapts competency standards in instruction, learning resources, and educational services. These results mean that the University of Cebu-Banilad's educational system, including the quality of the curriculum, instruction, support services, facilities, and resources, was appreciated by the graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) for the school year 2020 to 2023 since they served as an impetus in provide excellent educational training that enabled them to become competent nursing professionals and well-rounded individuals,

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.69 indicates that the respondents disclosed that the University of Cebu-Banilad College of Nursing has leadership among faculty in the service of the community. It can be gleaned from the preceding data that the educational training afforded to the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) students encompassed exposure to the community so that they can develop the value of helping the marginalized sector of society.

The aggregate mean of 3.73 shows that the respondents' assessment showed that, to a great extent, the University of Cebu College of Nursing goals were attained. The Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates for the school years 2020 to 2023 assessed that the University of Cebu-Banilad was successful in providing extensive educational systems that molded and trained students to become competent in nursing.

Table 22 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attributes stipulated in the College of Nursing core values.

The highest weighted mean of 3.90 shows that the respondents divulged that they manifested excellence to a great extent. It can be gleaned from this data that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates have confidence in showing outstanding nursing performance since they know that they received comprehensive and rigorous training based on theories, principles, and research results.

Table 22. Respondents' Manifestation of the Attributes Stipulated in the College of Nursing Core Values (n=52)

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1.	Nurturing	3.76	Greatly Manifested
2.	Unity	3.67	Greatly Manifested
3.	Respect	3.69	Greatly Manifested
4.	Service	3.85	Greatly Manifested
5.	Excellence	3.90	Greatly Manifested
	Aggregate Mean	3.77	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51-3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76-2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 -1.75-Not Manifested

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.67 indicates that the respondents disclosed that they manifested unity powerfully, which entails practicing collaboration, cooperation, and teamwork in providing excellent client care. The graduates possess the distinct abilities to work in teams or with their colleagues harmoniously and excellently towards achieving the goals of delivering nursing service to those who need it.

The aggregate mean of 3.77 shows that the respondents manifested to a great extent the attributes stipulated in the College of Nursing core values of nurturing, unity, respect, service, and excellence. These core values of the University of Cebu-Banilad College of Nursing were embedded in the curriculum, delivery of instructional, and curricular, co-curricular, and extra-curricular activities undertaken by the College of Nursing.

Table 23 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attributes stipulated in BSN's Program Educational Objectives (PEOs).

Table 23. Respondents 'Manifestation of the BSN Program Educational Objectives (PEOs) (n=52)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. demonstrate knowledge and skills in client care management in accordance with the Nurse's Code of Ethics and Legal Principles.	3.76	Greatly Manifested
2. practice as caring and compassionate clinical, community health, occupational health, private duty, and entrepreneurial nurses.	3.90	Greatly Manifested
3. integrate research findings to improve client care.	3.65	Greatly Manifested
Aggregate Mean	3.77	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

The highest weighted mean of 3.90 shows that the respondents divulged that, to a great extent, they could practice as caring and compassionate clinical, community health, occupational health, private duty, and entrepreneurial nurses. It can be deduced that the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program graduates at the University of Cebu-Banilad underwent extensive training wherein they could practice their profession in various fields of nursing.

Likewise, the lowest weighted mean of 3.65 indicates that the respondents disclosed that, to a great extent, they can integrate research findings to improve client care. The BSN graduates at UC-Banilad were able to translate the research findings into helpful nursing practice that addresses the clients' emerging and long-term health issues.

The aggregate mean of 3.77 shows that the respondents assessed that they manifested to a great extent the attributes stipulated in Program Educational Objectives (PEO) for the Bachelor of Science of Nursing (BSN). It can be deduced from the preceding results that the graduates of BSN at UC-Banilad successfully attained the expected competencies that should be learned in the curriculum, leading them to become successful nurses in practice and entrepreneurship.

Table 24 shows the respondents' assessments on the attainment of the Program Outcomes (POs) for the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN).

Table 24. Respondents' Assessments on the Attainment of the BSN Program Outcomes (POs)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. pass the Philippine Nurse Licensure Exam (PNLE).	3.96	Highly Attained
2. apply the nursing process and accurate documentation system in the interdisciplinary care of clients.	3.88	Highly Attained
3. observe the core values, bioethica principles and legal awareness cherished by the Nursing profession in the care of clients.	3.90	Highly Attained
4. engage in activities that promote professional and personal development	3.88	Highly Attained
5. participate in the development of policies and standards utilizing evidence-based practice.	3.78	Highly Attained
6. apply principles of partnership and collaboration to improve delivery of health care services .	3.96	Highly Attained
Aggregate Mean	3.81	Highly Attained

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Highly Attained; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Attained; 1.76-2.50 - Less Attained; 1.00 -1.75 - Not Attained

The highest weighted mean of 3.96 shows that the respondents assessed that enabling the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates to pass the Philippine Nurse Licensure Exam (PNLE) was highly attained by the University of Cebu College of Nursing since, over the years, the passing rate of BSN graduates was way above the national passing rate. This means that the quality of educational services provided to BSN students prepared them to pass the license examinations and become registered nurses successfully.

Another highest weighted mean of 3.96 shows that the respondents assessed that they can apply principles of partnership and collaboration to improve the delivery of health care services. This means that the BSN graduates of UC-Banilad possess the capabilities to forge cooperation with colleagues or healthcare professionals from other healthcare facilities to save lives or to optimize the provision of care to clients or patients.

Regarding broader scope, Kumar (2023) opined those strategic partnerships in healthcare involve collaborations between different organizations, sectors, or individuals to improve access to quality healthcare services. These partnerships bring together complementary expertise, resources, and perspectives to address healthcare systems' complex challenges. Organizations can leverage their strengths and overcome barriers by working together to provide better healthcare outcomes for individuals and communities (Kumar, 2023).

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.78 indicates that the respondents disclosed that, to a great extent, they can participate in developing policies and standards utilizing evidence-based practice. The BSN curriculum at the University of Cebu requires students to build valuable policies to improve the existing

healthcare or nursing systems. This means they were trained to translate nursing theories, policies, and concepts into helpful care plans, management frameworks, etc.

The aggregate mean of 3.81 shows that the respondents assessed that the stipulations in the Program Outcomes of BSN of the University of Cebu-Banilad were highly attained. The Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates expressed that they learned the various nursing competencies in demand in the nursing industry, which they leveraged as their competitive advantage when they worked in hospitals and other healthcare facilities in the Philippines and even abroad.

Table 25 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attributes stipulated in CHED Memorandum Order [CMO] No. 15 that is common to the business and management of Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates.

The highest weighted mean of 3.90 shows that the respondents divulged that they, to a great extent, applied guidelines and principles of evidence-based practice in care delivery. These results show that the performance of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad in their job was based on the scientific approach in nursing practice, which means that the applications of nursing theories in actual practice are based on research. The overarching aim of universal health coverage is for all people who need health services to access and receive high-quality care (Ngxongo & Masondo, 2022).

The World Health Organization [WHO] (2020) defines the quality of care as 'the degree to which health services for populations increase the likelihood of desired health outcomes and are consistent with evidence-based professional knowledge.' Therefore, quality of care can be measured and continuously improved by providing evidence-based care that considers the needs and preferences of service users.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.64 indicates that the respondents disclosed that to a moderate extent, current with global development in general, and nursing and health developments in particular, were applied in the job performance. These results denote that the BSN graduates of UC-Banilad continuously update their knowledge since they know that every now and then, there will be changes and innovations in the various facets of nursing.

Table 25. Respondents' Manifestation of the Attributes Stipulated in CMO No. 15 that is Specific to Bachelor of Science in Nursing (n=52)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
<i>A graduate of Bachelor of Science in Nursing is able to:</i>		
1. apply knowledge of physical, social, natural and health sciences, and humanities in the practice of nursing.	3.90	Greatly Manifested
2. perform safe, appropriate, and holistic care to individual families, population groups and community utilizing process	3.85	Greatly Manifested
3. apply guidelines and principles of evidence-based practice in the delivery of care.	3.94	Greatly Manifested
4. practice nursing in accordance with existing laws, legal, ethical and moral principles	3.83	Greatly Manifested
5. communicate effectively in speaking, writing and presenting using culturally-appropriate language.	3.79	Greatly Manifested
6. document to include reporting up-to-date client	3.85	Greatly

care accurately and comprehensively.			Manifested
7. collaborate effectively in collaboration with inter-, intra- and multi-disciplinary and multi-cultural teams.	3.83		Greatly Manifested
8. practice beginning management and leadership skills in delivery of client care using a systems approach.	3.83		Greatly Manifested
9. conduct research with an experienced	3.82		
10. researcher.	3.64		Greatly Manifested
engage in lifelong learning with a passion to keep			Greatly Manifested
11. current with and global development in general, and nursing and health developments in particular.	3.73		Manifested
12. demonstrate responsible citizenship and pride in being a Filipino.	3.67		Greatly Manifested
13. apply techno-intelligent care systems and health care delivery.	3.87		Manifested
14. uphold the nursing core values in the practice of profession.	3.81		Greatly Manifested
apply entrepreneurial skills in the delivery of nursing care.			Greatly Manifested
			Greatly Manifested
			Greatly Manifested
Aggregate Mean	3.80		Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 - 2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

The aggregate mean of 3.80 shows that the respondents manifested to a great extent the attributes of CHED Memorandum Order [CMO] No. 15, series of 2017 that is specific to the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) discipline. This means that the BSN graduates of UC-Banilad were well-rounded and competent in clinical practice, education, research, and leadership.

Table 26 shows the respondents' manifestation of the attributes stipulated in CHED Memorandum Order [CMO] No. 15 for a graduate Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN).

The highest weighted mean of 3.92 shows that the respondents divulged that, to a great extent, they integrated relevant principles of social, physical, natural, and health sciences and humanities in a given health and nursing education. The graduates of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) of the University of Cebu-Banilad possessed competencies in combining the various knowledge, ideas, and philosophies of life in the context of performing their job and that all facets of life are considered in providing holistic care to the client or patients.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean of 3.83 indicates that the respondents disclosed that, to a great extent, they can assess client's (individual, family, population group, and/or community), one's health. The BSN graduates of UC-Banilad possessed the competencies and skills to evaluate the current status of health based on their knowledge and limits as healthcare practitioners.

Table 26. Respondents' Assessments on the Manifestation of the Performance of Nursing (n=52)

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Integrating relevant principles of social, physical, natural and health sciences and humanities in a given health and nursing education.	3.92	Greatly Manifested
2. Applying appropriate nursing concepts and actions holistically and comprehensively.	3.90	Greatly Manifested
3. Assessing with the client (individual, family, population group, and/or community), one's health.	3.83	Greatly Manifested
4. Formulating with the client a plan of care to address the health conditions, needs, problems and issues.	3.85	Greatly Manifested
5. Implementing safe and quality interventions with the client to address the health needs, problems and issues.	3.90	Greatly Manifested
Aggregate Mean	3.88	Greatly Manifested

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Greatly Manifested; 2.51 -3.25 - Moderately Manifested; 1.76 -2.50 - Less Manifested; 1.00 - 1.75 - Not Manifested

Quality healthcare ensures that people receive accurate diagnoses, effective treatments, and compassionate care. It can greatly improve health outcomes, increase life expectancy, and enhance the overall quality of life (Kumar, 2023).

The aggregate mean of 3.88 shows that the respondents disclosed that, to a great extent, they manifested the performance indicators for nursing. It can be inferred that the BSN graduates of UC-Banilad had exemplary competencies and skills to perform their assigned based on the set performance indicators in the organizations where they are employed. Likewise, they can translate nursing theories into evidence-based practice for optimal client care.

Healthcare organizations can set broad key performance indicators (KPIs) to track performance across the facility and designate indicators within specific departments or areas of the company. Nurses significantly impact patient experience and medical outcomes in most healthcare settings, often defining the organization's success through their work. Nursing KPIs can be used to reveal critical areas of achievement or opportunities for improvement. Nursing KPIs are performance indicators set against operating standards within the Nursing department. These track a number of fundamental metrics that impact or are impacted directly by your organization's nurses (Ko, n.d.).

Conclusions

Based on the salient findings of this tracer study, the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) graduates of the University of Cebu-Banilad (UC-Banilad) for the school years 20120-2020 were employable in the healthcare industry due to the excellent education provided to the students, while anchoring on the four-focal functions of the University, such as instruction, research, community extension, and production. Also, the

various exposures of the students in the clinical and community enabled them to practice their nursing profession in multiple fields such as public health nursing, occupational health nursing, private duty nursing, and home care nursing. Likewise, they exhibited the expected competencies of professional nurses as indicated in the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) curriculum, the CHED Memorandum Order No. 15, series of 2017, the University's vision, mission, institutions goals, the College of Nursing's vision, mission, goals and core values. Hence, the BSN curriculum of UC is aligned with the established standards of regulatory bodies and the requirements of the healthcare industry in the Philippines and even in the global arena.

Translational Research

Concerning the essential results of this study, a program-level intervention plan shall be devised to encompass periodic review and revision of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) curriculum of the University of Cebu-Banilad to ensure that it is compliant with the regulatory standards and addresses the current healthcare industry requirements and needs. It shall integrate feasible programs and activities to ensure that the nursing education aligns with the requirements of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), hospital partners, the healthcare industry, and the community where the graduates will exercise their nursing profession. Also, the plan shall intensify measures to prepare the students to pass the Philippine Nurse Licensure Examination (PNLE) and other examinations they will take for a promising nursing career here in the Philippines and abroad.

REFERENCES

- Abbott, K., & Snidal, D. (2021). *The spectrum of international institutions: An interdisciplinary collaboration on global governance*. Routledge. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3DVzgLw>.
- Aggarwal, R., & Ranganathan, P. (2019). Study designs: Part 2- Descriptive studies. *Perspect. Clin. Res.* 10(1), 34-36. doi: [10.4103/picr.PICR_154_18](https://doi.org/10.4103/picr.PICR_154_18).
- Agasisti, T., Dal Bianco, A., Landoni, P., Sala, A., & Salerno, M. (2011). Evaluating the efficiency of research in academic departments: An empirical analysis in an Italian region. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 65(3), 267-289. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2273.2011.00489.x>.
- Albert, J.R. (2013). *Is education in sync with labor?* Beyond Numbers. National Statistical Coordination Board [NSCB]. Retrieved from http://www.nscb.gov.ph/beyondthenumbers/2013/01112013_jrga_educlab_or.asp.
- Almejas, B.C., Marasigan, J.C., Morante, T.A. Lim, E.J.A., & Catuday, R.A. (2017). *Teacher education graduates: A tracer study*. Education and Corporate Social Responsibility, Cebu, Philippines. International Conference on Law, Business, Education and Corporate Responsibility (LBECSSR-17), September 21-22, 2017, Cebu, Philippines.

- American Association of Colleges of Nursing. (2019). *Your nursing career: A look at the facts*. AAC Nursing Org. Retrieved from <https://www.aacnursing.org/Students/Your-Nursing-Career-A-Look-at-the-Facts>.
- Appiah, S. (2020). Quality of nursing education programme in the Philippines: faculty members perspectives. *BMC Nurs.*, 19, 110. doi: [10.1186/s12912-020-00508-9](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-020-00508-9).
- Aquino, A.B., Punongbayan, E.J., Macalaguim, L.P., Bauyon, S.M. Rodriguez Jr., R.A., & Quizon, G.R. (2015). Teacher education graduate tracer study from 2010 to 2014 in one state university in Batangas, Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(5), pp. 45-50.
- Austria, J.S. (2023). Tracer study of the nursing graduates in a state college. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 4(9). [10.11594/ijmaber.04.09.20](https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.04.09.20).
- Badiru, E.O. & Wahome, M. (2016). Conducting graduate tracer studies for quality assurance in east African Universities: A focus on graduate students voices on the quality culture. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(6). Retrieved from www.iiste.org.
- Bandura A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychol. Rev.*, 84, 191–215. doi: 10.1037/0033-295X.84.2.191.
- Bandura A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
- Bandura, A. (1993). Perceived self-efficacy in cognitive development and functioning. *Educational Psychologist*, 28(2), 117-148.
- Bandura. A. (1995) (eds). *Self-efficacy in changing societies*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bandura A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: the exercise of control*. New York: W. H. Freeman and Company.
- Bandura A. (1997). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychol. Rev.*, 84, 191–215. doi: 10.1037/0033-295X.84.2.191.

- Bandura, A. (2012). On the functional properties of perceived self-efficacy revisited. *Journal of Management*, 38, 9–44. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206311410606>.
- Banua, A.S. (2017). Determinants of performance of nursing graduates in licensure examination. *BUR & D Journal*. Retrieved from https://journal.bicol-u.edu.ph/assets/journal_pdf/8%20Banua_113-118.pdf.
- Barnett, R. (2009). Knowing and becoming in the higher education curriculum. *Stud. High. Educ.*, 34(4), 429-440, 10.1080/03075070902771978.
- Bauman, Z. (2007). *Liquid times: Living in an age of uncertainty*. Cambridge, UK: Polity Press.
- Bell, S. (2010). Project-based learning for the 21st century: Skills for the future. *The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies*, 83 (2), 39-43. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00098650903505415>.
- Bengan, K.C. (2011). The plight of nursing education in the Philippines. *HubPages*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/bwNP5>.
- Benner, P. Sutphen, M., Leonard, V., & Day, L. (2010). *Educating nurses: A call for radical transformation*. Jossey-Bass, San Francisco.
- Billings, D.M., & Halstead, J.A. (2012). *Teaching in nursing: A guide for faculty* (4th ed). Elsevier, St. Louis, MO.
- Billett, S., Harteis, C., & Grube, H. (2014). *International handbook of research in professional and practice-based learning*. Springer.
- Brosola (n. d.). *A tracer study of bachelor of science in nursing graduates at National University*. National University. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/RVCXd>.
- Brown P., & A. Hesketh. (2004). *The management of talent: Employability and jobs in the knowledge economy*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199269532.001.0001>.
- Brown, V. A., & Lambert, J. A. (2012). *Collective learning for transformational change: A guide to collaborative action*. Routledge.

- Bvumbwe, T. (2016). Enhancing nursing education via academic–clinical partnership: An integrative review. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences* 3, 314-322.
- Cole, J.A., & Tibby, V. (2012). *Employer and student perception employability*. York: Higher Education Academy.
- Chertkovskaya, E., Watt, P., Tramer, S., & Spoelstra, S. (2013). Employability. *Ephemera*, 13(4). Retrieved from <http://ray.yorks.ac.uk/id/eprint/1985/1/13-4ephemera-nov13.pdf>.
- Cherry, K. (2024). Self efficacy and why believing in yourself matters. *Personality Psychology. Very-Well Mind*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/RcZyk>.
- Commission on Higher Education [CHED]. (2017). *Policies, standards and guidelines for the bachelor of science in nursing (BSN) program*. CHED Memorandum Order No. 15, Series of 2017. Retrieved from <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/CMO-15-s-2017.pdf>.
- Crisostomo, S. (2013, February 1). Group hits commercialization of nursing education. *The Philippine Star*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/gGPR4>.
- Crisp, G., Higgs, J., & Letts, W. (2019). The employability agenda. In *Learning for Future Possibilities; Higgs, J., Letts, W., Crisp, G., Eds.; Education for employability; Brill: Leiden, The Netherlands*, 2, pp. 3–12.
- Cuadra, L.J., Aure, M.R.K.L., & Gonzaga, G.L. (2019). The use of tracer study improving undergraduate programs in the university. *Asia Pacific Higher Education Research Journal (APHERJ)*, 6(1).
- Deci, E.L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. New York: Plenum.
- Dewi, N.R., Listiaji, P., Taufiq, M., Savitri, E.N., Yanitama, A., & Herianti, A.P. (2021). Development of a tracer study system for graduates of the Integrated Science Department, Universitas Negeri Semarang. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1918 (4). Article 042010, 10.1088/1742-6596/1918/4/042010.

- Dotong, C. I., Chavez, N. H., Camella, N. C., De Castro, E. L., Prenda, M. T. B., Laguador, J. M. (2016). Tracer study of engineering graduates of one higher education institution in the philippines for academic year 2009-2012. *European Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 4(4). Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/rEpFU>.
- Du, M.R. (2019). A tracer study among nursing graduates of LPU-St. Cabrini School of Health Sciences, Inc. SY 2011-2016. *LPU-Laguna Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(3). Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/bnpFT>.
- Dumlao, L. A. (2006). Employability and earnings of graduates of degree and non-degree program and job relevance to their schooling. *The Search Journal*. Quezon City.
- Eccles, J. (1983). Expectancies, values, and academic behaviors. In J. T. Spence (Ed.), *Achievement and achievement motives: Psychological and sociological approaches* (pp. 75-146). San Francisco, CA: W. H. Freeman.
- Eccles, J.S., & Wigfield, A. (2002). Motivational beliefs, values, and goals. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53, 109-132.
- Egesah, O.B., & Wahome, M. N. (2017). University students' learning experiences: Nuanced voices from graduate tracer study. *Journal of Higher Education in Africa/Revue l'enseignement supérieur en Afrique*, 15(1), 43-56.
- Ehrenberg, R., Smith, R., & Hallock, K. (2021). *Modern labor economics: Theory and public policy*. Routledge.
- Fernando, E.J.N. (2023). Graduate tracer study of bachelor of science in computer engineering in a private university. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research*, 6(10), 8-27. DOI - <http://doi.org/10.37502/IJSMR.2023.61002>.
- Fletcher-Brown, J., Knibbs, K., & Middleton, K. (2015). Developing “employagility”: The 3Es case for live-client learning. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*.
- Fakunle, O., & Hingson, H. (2021). Interrogating theoretical and empirical approaches to employability in different global regions. *Higher Education Quarterly*. Wiley Online Library. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hequ.12345>.

- Fawaz, M., Hamdan-Mansour, A., & Tassi, A. (2018). Challenges facing nursing education in the advanced healthcare environment. *International Journal of Africa Nursing Sciences*, 9, 105-110.
- Fernandez, D. (2022). Unemployment rate up to 6% in May. *Inquirer.net*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/nLvIq>.
- Finn, D. (2000) 'From full employment to employability: A new deal for Britain's unemployed?' *International Journal of Manpower*, 21(5), 384-99.
- Fleuren, B.P.I., de Grip, A., Jansen, N.W.H., Kant, I., & Zijlstra, F.R.H. (2020). Unshrouding the sphere from the clouds: Towards a comprehensive conceptual framework for sustainable employability. *Sustainability*, 12, 6366.
- Gerwe, O. (2021). The Covid-19 pandemic and the accommodation sharing sector: Effects and prospects for recovery. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 167, 120733. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120733>.
- Gonzales, N. (2013). Graduate tracer study. *Knowledge Community*. Retrieved from http://knowledgecommunity.ph/?page_id=43.
- Guilbert, L. (2015). Employability: Review and research prospects. *International Journal for Educational Vocational Guidance*, 16, 69-89. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10775-015-9288-4>.
- Guinid, J. T., Anicas, M.P., Nero, F.D., Talindan, G.A., & Tabudlo, J.B. (2019). *Employment status of the bachelor of science in nursing graduates of the University of Northern Philippines Batch 2014-2016*. Surabaya International Health Conference, Novotel Samtor East Surabaya Hotel, July 13-14, 2010.
- Hafiz, M., & Dewayani, E. (2020, December). Development of Tarumanagara University tracer study information system. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 1007(1), p. 012117). IOP Publishing.
- Harter, S. (1981) A new self-report scale of intrinsic vs extrinsic motivation in the classroom. *Developmental Psychology*, 17(3), 302-312.
- Hazaymeh, E., & Dela Peña, M. (2017). A tracer study of La Salle University College of Engineering graduates. *Academia*, 18(1), 52-68.

- Hénard, F., & Roseveare, D. (2012). Fostering quality teaching in higher education: Policies and practices. *An IMHE Guide for Higher Education Institutions*, 1(1), 7-11. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3EkN8P1>.
- Hinchliffe, G.W., & Jolly, A. (2013). Graduate identity and employability. *British Educational Research Journal*, August. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411926.2010.482200>.
- Hipona, J.B., Cuevas, J.E.T., & Martin, J.A. (2021). A tracer study of the bachelor of science in nursing program of La Consolacion University Philippine graduates: A reflection on institutional goals. *An International Journal of Art & Higher Education: A Refereed Research Journal*, 10(1). doi:10.46360/cosmos.ahe.520211004.
- Holmes, L. (2015). Becoming a graduate: The warranting of an emergent identity. *Educ. Train.*, 57, 219–238.
- Howard, C. (2010, July 9). The nursing profession under siege. *ABSCBNnews.com*. Retrieved October 18, 2013 From <http://www.abcnnews.com/-depth/07/09/10/nursing-profession-under-siege>.
- International Labour Organization [ILO]. (2022). Recovery in youth employment is still lagging, says ILO. *Global Employment Trends for the Youth*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/9ufhi>.
- Ismail, S., & Mohammed, D.S. (2015). Employability skills in TVET curriculum in Nigeria Federal Universities of Technology. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 204, 73-80. 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.08.111.
- Iwasiw, C.L., & Goldenberg, D. (2015). *Curriculum development in nursing education* (3rd ed.). Jones & Bartlett Learning, Burlington, MA.
- Jackson, D. (2015). Employability skill development in work-integrated learning: Barriers and best practice. *Studies in Higher Education*, 40(2), 350-367. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2013.842221>.
- Jayasingam, S., FujiwaraY., & Thurasamy, R. (2016). I am competent so I can be choosy’: Choosiness and its implication on graduate employability. *Studies in Higher Education*, 43(7). <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2016.1221918>.

- Johnes, J. (2006). Data envelopment analysis and its application to the measurement of efficiency in higher education. *Economics of Education Review*. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3R0NZrG>.
- Johnston, K. (2009). The importance of the baccalaureate degree in nursing education. *Peoria Magazine.com*. Retrieved October 18, 2013 from <https://shorturl.at/dsVX9>.
- Keating, S.B. (2014). *Curriculum development and evaluation in nursing* (3rd ed.). Springer, NY.
- Kebedom, N. (2010). *Sheba university graduates' tracer study*. Sheba University College. Retrieved from <http://www.suc.edu.et/TracerStudy.html>.
- Kift, S. (2019). Employability and higher education: Keeping calm in the face of disruptive innovation. In *The employability agenda*; Jiggs, J., Crisp, G., Letts, W., Eds.; Education for Employability; Brill Sense: Leiden, The Netherlands, 2019; Volume 1, pp. 49–6.
- Kanter, R. M. (1989) *When giants learn to dance: Mastering the challenges of strategy, management and careers in the 1990s*. New York: Simon and Schuster.
- Knibbs, K., Fletcher-Brown, J., & Middleton, K. Z. (2015). Introducing Employability– sharing ideas for engaging multiple stakeholders in the teaching, learning, employment journey. *British Academy of Management Conference*. University of Southampton Institutional Repository. Retrieved from <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/427804/>.
- Knight, P.T., & Yorke, M. (2004). *Learning, curriculum and employability in higher education*. London and New York: RoutledgeFalmer.
- Ko, M. (n.d.). Nursing kpi dashboard. *Crosschq*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/EMLnd>.
- Kumar, K. (2023). The impact of strategic partnerships on improving access to quality healthcare services. *Linkedin*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/wAe0f>.
- Landeen, J., Carr, D., Culver, K., Martin, L., Matthew-Maich, N., Noesgard, C., & Beney-Gadsby, L. (2016). The impact of curricular changes on BSCN students' clinical learning outcomes. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 21, 51-58. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2016.09.010>.
- Leaper, C. (2011). More similarities than difference in contemporary theories of social development. In *Advances in child development and behavior*. Science Direct. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/bookseries/advances-in-child-development-and-behavior>.

- Leberman, S., & McDonald L. (2016). The transfer of learning: Participants' perspectives of adult education and training. CRC Press. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3YGY1I2>.
- Lucitasari, D. R., & Khannan, M. S. A. (2019). Designing mobile alumni tracer study system using waterfall method: an Android based. *International Journal of Computer Networks and Communications Security*, 7(9), 196-202.
- Luthans, F. (2002). Positive organizational behavior. Developing and managing psychological strengths. *Academy of Management Executive*, 16(1), 57-72. <http://doi.org/10.5465/AME.2002.6640181>.
- Marmolejo, F. (2016). *What matters most for tertiary education: A framework paper*. Working Paper Series, Number 11. World Bank Group.
- Maryville University. (2023). *What is a nurse entrepreneur, and how do you become one?* Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/IHTjr>.
- Mason, W., & Watts, D. J. (2009, June). *Financial incentives and the" performance of crowds"*. In Proceedings of the ACM SIGKDD Workshop On Human Computation. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3dFgRbh>.
- McCowan, T. (2015). Should universities promote employability? *Theory and Reserch in Education*, 13(3), 267-285. . <https://doi.org/10.1177/1477878515598060>.
- Mitchinson, A., & Morris, R. (2014). *Learning about learning agility*. White Paper.Center for Creative Leadership.
- Mwakigonja, A. R. (2016). The Doctor of medicine curriculum review at the school of medicine, Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania: A tracer study report from 2009. *BMC Medical Education*, 16(1), 223.
- Ngxongo, T.S.P., & Masondo, J.N.M. (2022). Nurse managers' experiences regarding the use of key performance indicators in developing work plans. *Afr. J. Prim. Health Care Fa. Med.*, 14(1), 3556. doi: [10.4102/phcfm.v14i1.3556](https://doi.org/10.4102/phcfm.v14i1.3556).
- Ofoha, D., & Iwuchukwu, O. (2018). Employers' perception and expectations of professional competency of distance learning graduates: A tracer study of nursing graduates of the national Open University

of Nigeria (NOUN). *Open Praxis*, 10(3), 265-278.
<https://search.informit.org/doi/abs/10.3316/informit.985565139301032>.

Okay-Somerville, B., & Scholarios, D. (2017). Position, possession or process? Understanding objective and subjective employability during university-to-work transitions. *Stud. High. Educ.*, 42, 1275–1291.

Oliver, B. (2015). Redefining graduate employability and work-integrated learning: Proposals for effective higher education in disrupted economies. *Journal of Teaching and Learning for Graduate Employability*, 6(1), 56-65.

Orejana, A.J., & Resurrection, P.F. (2010). Tracer study on the graduates on the bsba program: An input to curricular development. *The Mindanao Forum*, 23(1). <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=7051>.

Paadi, K. (2014). Perceptions on employability skills necessary to enhance human resource management graduate prospects of securing a relevant place in the labor market. *European Scientific Journal*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2014.v10n10p%25p>.

Pool, L., & Sewell, P. (2007). *The key to employability: developing a practical model of graduate employability*. *Education+ Training*. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3DJTF6t>.

Quinto, L., & Posada, A. L. (2020). A tracer study among medical technology graduates of LPU-St. Cabrini School of Health Sciences, Inc. *LPU-Laguna Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(1). Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/rpWCX>

Ramirez, T.L., Cruz, L.T., & Alcantara, N.V. (2014). Tracer study of RTU graduates: An analysis. *Researchers World*, 5(1), pp. 66-76.

Regmi, P.P. (2009). *Tracer study of AIT graduates 2003-2008*. *Asian Institute of Technology (AIT) Klong Luang, Pathumthani, Thailand*. Retrieved from <http://www.docstoc.com/docs/162623073/TRACER-STUDY---Asian-Institute-of-Technology>.

Romgens, I., Scoupe, R., & Beusaert, S. (2019). Unraveling the concept of employability, bringing together research on employability in higher education and the workplace. *Studies in Higher Education*, 45(12), 2588-2603. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2019.1623770>.

- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25, 54-67. doi:10.1006/ceps.1999.1020.
- Ryan, R. M., & Stiller, J. (1991). The social contexts of internalization: Parent and teacher influences on autonomy, motivation and learning. In P. R. Pintrich & M. L. Maehr (Eds.), *Advances in motivation and achievement* (Vol. 7, pp. 115–149). Greenwich, CT: JAI Press.
- Salaria, N. (2012). Meaning of the term-descriptive survey research method. *International Journal of Transformations in Business Management*, 2(2). Retrieved from https://ijtbm.com/admin/upload/Apr_2012_NEERU%20SALARIA%202.pdf.
- Sanchez, M.P.R., & Diamante, V.A.M. (2017). Graduate tracer study of the college of nursing. *The Malaysian Journal of Journal of Nursing*, 8(3), 41-47. Retrieved from <https://ejournal.lucp.net/index.php/mjn/article/view/47>.
- Schleicher, A. (2012). *Preparing teachers and developing school leaders for the 21st century: Lessons from around the world*. 2, rue Andre Pascal, F- 75775 Paris Cedex 16, France: OECD Publishing.
- Schomburg, H. (2011). *Employability and mobility of bachelor graduates in Europe: Key results of the Bologna process*. Netherlands: Sense Publishers.
- Schomburg, H. (2016). *Carrying out tracer studies: Guide to anticipating and matching skills and job* (Vol. 6). European Training Foundation. European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training. International Labour Office.
- Shawcross, J., & Ridgman, T. (2012). Manufacturing excellent engineers: Skill development in a masters programme. *Engineering Education*. DOI: 10.11120/ened.2012.07020038.
- Soares, I.D.S.M., Monteiro, A., & Proenca, J. (2017). *Learning outcomes and employability: A case study on management academic programmes*. INTED2017 Proceedings.DOI: 10.21125/inted.2017.1518.
- Soares, B., Preto, R., & Reis, L. (2016). Mechanical behavior of basalt fibers in a basalt-UP composite. *Procedia Structural Integrity*, 1, 82-89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2016.02.012>.
- Sumanasiri, E. A. G. (2011). *Succeeding in the Indian market: Exploring the critical factors on market performance*. In Proceedings of International Conference on Business Management, 8.

- Tabbuac, P.M. (2010). *Follow-up study of the master of business administration and master in public administration graduates of the University of Northern Philippines*. (Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City).
- Taylor, D.C.M., & Hamdy, H. (2013). Adult learning theories: Implications for learning and teaching in medical education. AMEE Guide No. 83. *Medical Teacher*, 35(11), e1561- e1572. <https://doi.org/10.3109/0142159X.2013.828153>.
- Teresa-Morales, C., Rodríguez-Pérez, M., & Ramos-Pichardo, J. D. (2023). Reasons for choosing and completing nursing studies among incoming and outgoing students: A qualitative study. *Nurse Education Today*, 125. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2023.105794>.
- Tertiary Education Commission. [TEC]. (2009). *A comparative analysis of the graduate tracer studies 1996 and 2008*. Retrieved from http://www.tec.mu/pdf_downloads/pubrep/comparative%20analysis%20GTS.pdf.
- The World Bank. (2017, October 05). *Higher education*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/tertiaryeducation#1>.
- Torres, C. A., & Schugurensky, D. (2002). The political economy of higher education in the era of neoliberal globalization: Latin America in comparative perspective. *Higher Education*, 43(4), 429-455.
- Trading Economics. (2019). *Philippines' unemployment rate*. Retrieved from <https://tradingeconomics.com/Philippines/unemployment-rate>.
- Tran, T.T. (2015). Is graduate employability the 'whole-of-higher-education-issue'? *Journal of Education and Work*. Retrieved from <https://bit.ly/3S6aM6Q>.
- Trines, S. (2018). Mobile nurses: Trends in international labor migration in the nursing field. *World Education News and Reviews*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/hsvwy>.
- Van, V. (2020). Social responsibility of students: The role and importance of education. *Journal of Natural Remedies*, 972-5547.
- Voxco. (2021). *Decoding the charm of descriptive surveys*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/O5JbJ>.

- Wahome, M., Egesah, O., & Wanyama, M. (2015, March). Entrenching quality assurance culture through graduate tracer studies in East Africa: Lessons learnt, challenges and prospects from Mutrace. *International Journal of Education Learning and Development*, 3(2), 15-24. Retrieved October 8, 2016, from www.eajournals.org.
- Weiner, P., Baukens, M., Bollerot, P., Pineschi-Gapenne, M., & Walwei, U. (2017). *Empoyability: from theory and practice* (International Social Security Series volume 7). New Yoek: Routledge.
- Wigfield, A. (1994). Expectancy-value theory of achievement motivation: A development perspective. *Educational Psychologist*, 6(1), 49–78.
- Williams, S., Dodd, L.J., Steele, C., & Randall, R. (2016). A systematic review of current understandings of employability. *Journal of Education and work*, 29(80), 877-890. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2015.1102210>.
- World Health Organization [WHO]. *World health statistics 2020: Monitoring health for the SDGs, sustainable development goals* Geneva: World Health Organization.
- Yorke, M. (2006). *Employability in higher education: what it is – what it is not*. York: Higher Education Academy.
- Zimmerman, J. (2012, January 31). Are college students learning?. *Los Angeles Times*. Retrieved from <https://shorturl.at/dHJW7>.